

Theoretical and Philosophical Article

Socio-politics of Mathematics Teacher Beliefs: A Panoptic Consideration

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ABSTRACT: In this theoretical paper, we draw on Panopticism (Foucault, 1975/1995) to consider how an emphasis on productive beliefs for teaching and, especially, the practices of measuring, categorizing, and correcting beliefs through research and teacher education create and sustain mechanisms of power within mathematics education. We highlight examples from the existing research on mathematics teachers' beliefs as well as data collected from a small group of teachers

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to describe possible distributions of power. Through the instruments that researchers create and use to measure beliefs and the beliefs that we, as educators, collectively value as productive (our Panopticon), the functioning of power becomes bigger than any one teacher, researcher, or teacher educator.

KEYWORDS: beliefs, in-service teacher education, poststructuralism, Panopticon

Consider these three imagined interactions between mathematics teachers and mathematics education researchers (or teacher educators).

- 1) Given two belief statements on a survey and asked to mark where they fall on a continuum between them, a mathematics teacher marks the box closest to the statement “my job as a mathematics instructor is to teach students how to calculate and find answers to problems without using technology” (Adamson et al., n.d.).
- 2) A mathematics teacher says, “Developing conceptual understanding is key in my class!” in an interview (modified from NCTM, 2014).
- 3) A mathematics teacher says, “All of my students are children of God” during a class observation (see Johnson et al., 2021).

We expect a range of possible emotions and subsequent actions from researchers and/or teacher educators; however, we also expect the normalized responses to be, as follows: 1) negative emotions such as sadness or anger accompanied by a desire to challenge this belief; 2) positive emotions such as happiness accompanied by a desire to affirm this belief;⁴ 3) tension accompanied by silence as typically religious ideologies are not discussed in schools. What if, however, in the first scenario, the teacher has limited access to technology, including the use of cell phones in the classroom? What if, in the second scenario, the emphatic point the teacher was making is that conceptual understanding is only for her class of students, who are “gifted”? What if, the teacher in the third scenario, is using their deeply held religious beliefs as the primary lens for how they view the capacities of the students in their class?

Teacher educators and educational researchers have an interest in evaluating teachers’ dispositions and beliefs and, therefore, have developed various ways of generating data⁵ and theories on teachers’ dispositions or beliefs (e.g., Aguirre & Speer, 2000; Akkoç et al., 2016; An et al., 2017; Boyd & Ash, 2018; Harrison & Lakin, 2018; Itter & Meyers, 2017; Leder & Forgasz, 2002; Philipp, 2007; Xenofontos, 2018; Yan & Cheng, 2015). In mathematics education in the United States, these kinds of studies have been used to develop lists of unproductive and productive beliefs for mathematics teaching in published materials by the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (2014). For example, in a discussion of mathematics curriculum, the statement “mathematics is a static, unchanging field” is listed as an “unproductive belief” (NCTM, 2014, p. 72). In contrast to this stated belief, the “productive” analog states: “Mathematics is a dynamic field that is ever changing. Emphases in the curriculum are evolving, and it is important to embrace and adapt to appropriate changes” (NCTM, 2014, p. 72). In another example, an

⁴ We acknowledge the research on teacher emotion (and therefore, teacher educator emotion) might argue against the use of the labels of “positive” or “negative” for emotions. We use these words here in a more vernacular way and acknowledge here that these labels come from what is normalized in society. For more reading on teacher emotions, see Zembylas (2003, 2005).

⁵ We use the term “generate,” rather than “collect,” to refer to the production of data as part of research because we feel that “collect” suggests that the researcher gathers pre-existing, objective knowledge whereas “generate” acknowledges that data does not exist until created by the researcher and/or research participants. Our choice of terminology aligns with a poststructural perspective.

“unproductive” belief about equity and access states, “Equity is the same as equality. All students need to receive the same learning opportunities so that they can achieve the same academic outcomes” (NCTM, 2014, p. 63). The “productive” analog to this belief is listed as “Equity is attained when students receive the differentiated supports (e.g., time, instruction, curricular materials, programs) necessary to ensure that all students are mathematically successful” (NCTM, 2014, p. 63).

Subjecting individual mathematics teachers to this division between “unproductive” and “productive” beliefs for teaching relies on an automatic and taken-for-granted functioning of power. Foucault (1975/1995) introduced Panopticism as a way to understand how mechanisms of power can function automatically and pervasively. Originally developed by Jeremy Bentham in the late 18th century, the Panopticon was a building designed to monitor prisoners. The Panopticon has a tower situated at the center of the prison, always visible to all inmates, who could never discern whether or not they were being watched by individuals inside the tower. The power of the Panopticon lay in being both “visible and unverifiable” (Foucault, 1975/1995, p. 201). In other words, individuals measure, supervise, and correct their own behaviors (i.e., discipline themselves) based on the perceived presence of this perpetual surveillance. Foucault (1975/1995) argued Panopticism extends beyond prison to other institutions, including schools.

In this theoretical paper, we draw on Panopticism (Foucault, 1975/1995) to consider how an emphasis on productive beliefs for teaching and, especially, the practices of measuring, categorizing, and correcting beliefs through research and teacher education create and sustain mechanisms of power within mathematics education. We highlight examples from the existing research on mathematics teachers’ beliefs as well as data collected from a small group of teachers to describe possible distributions of power. Through the instruments that researchers create and use to measure beliefs and the beliefs that we, as educators, collectively value as productive (our Panopticon), the functioning of power becomes bigger than any one teacher, researcher, or teacher educator.

We want to acknowledge upfront that we make our primary arguments from our own perspectives in the United States. We will make connections to and raise questions about and for other countries in the discussion section. We understand there are limitations with this approach; however, we also want to write and argue from a place and context that we understand. Adopting this perspective, then, fundamentally relies on the knowledge that the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) has an important position in the discourse of mathematics education for scholars and teachers and other stakeholders in the United States.

Theoretically Framing Our Consideration of Mathematics Education Research on Beliefs

We recognize that research on mathematics teacher beliefs (which we review in a later section) has primarily been framed by constructivist theories of learning. Some scholars have adopted more sociocultural approaches to considering teacher beliefs (e.g., Skott, 2009). As we considered our data and the existing research, questions like those we posed in response to the imagined scenarios in the introduction began to circulate in our collective discussions. We knew that our typical lenses of criticality were influencing these questions. Therefore, we see our work as a response to other scholars’ calls to examine mathematics education through a lens of criticality and poststructuralism (Nasir & Hand, 2006; Nasir & de Royston, 2013; Stinson & Bullock, 2012; Valero, 2004). Further, we position our work alongside philosophical contributions and theoretical analyses of various

aspects of the teaching and learning of mathematics as well as the research in mathematics education (e.g., Bowers, 2022; de Freitas, 2016; Harper et al., 2021; Parks, 2010).

Poststructural, philosophical, and critical lenses have been adopted to describe, analyze, and critique diverse aspects of the teaching and learning of mathematics (e.g., Bowers, 2022; de Freitas, 2016; Harper et al., 2021; Parks, 2010; Popkewitz, 2004; Strachler-Pohl et al., 2016; Stinson & Bullock, 2012; Walkerdine, 1990; Walshaw, 2001, 2004b). For example, poststructuralism has been used to examine mathematics itself as a discipline (e.g., Ernest, 2004; Fleener, 2004), facets of mathematics education research (e.g., Kolloche, 2016, 2018; Meaney, 2004; Pais & Valero, 2012; Stinson & Bullock, 2012; Valero, 2004), students' interactions with mathematical content (e.g., Cabral, 2004; Popkewitz, 2004; Walkerdine, 1990), and mathematics teachers' pedagogical practices (e.g., Dubbs & Herbel-Eisenmann, 2021; Walshaw, 2004a). For a more detailed coverage of the research using Foucault, specifically, see Kolloche (2016). Here, we highlight four articles to describe the range of ideas that have been examined through poststructuralism, broadly, and using the ideas of Foucault, specifically, in order to position our own work with respect to these uses.

Stinson and Bullock (2012) described similarities and differences historically across the shifts in theoretical assumptions in mathematics education. Of particular relevance for our work is their comparing and contrasting of critical theories and poststructuralist theories. They argued that these theories can be used together to challenge the status quo in mathematics education research. They stated, "concepts from both theoretical perspectives might be used side by side in research—like tools pulled from a tool box—to short-circuit systems of power (Foucault, 1975/1995) inherent in mathematics teaching and learning" (p. 45). Meaney (2004) examined her own role interacting with members of the Indigenous community she was studying, of which she is not a member. Specifically, she used Foucault's discussions of power in order to develop a framework for considering the multiple relationships she had and how those intersected in complex ways. Walkerdine (1990) raised questions, using Foucault's ideas and other poststructuralist thinking, about the assumptions made about students engaging in the learning of mathematics and the discipline of mathematics itself. She stated:

How do our ideas of "real mathematics" and of mathematical "truth" become incorporated into the "truth" about the human subject which is used in the regulation of the social. [sic] The "truth" of reason and reasoning, of the world as a book written in the language of mathematics, become important aspects of historically-specific regimes of truth. Carraher [1989] discusses this issue, but Foucault's idea of "truth" is useful because it allows us to link that mathematical "truth" with the "truths" in forms of management and government which aim to regulate the subject. So, for example, when Carraher tells us that Brazilian street children did not solve a problem by one-to-one correspondence we are left little option but to pathologise them since we have no other (socially and historically specific) theories on offer. (Walkerdine, 1990, p. 52)

Here, Walkerdine specifically challenged the way we, in the field of mathematics education, make assumptions which result in blaming students for their lack of abilities. Dubbs and Herbel-Eisenmann (2021) described the evolution of teachers' discourse practices. They used Foucault's ideas of "techniques of surveillance and modalities of power" (Dubbs & Herbel-Eisenmann, 2021, abstract) to illuminate how teachers' use of other practices such as shushing the students decreased when teachers focused on developing student discourse in the classroom through the use of teacher discourse moves (Herbel-Eisenmann et al., 2017).

We admit when we embarked on the discussion of these ideas in this paper seven years ago, we were fairly novice to the use of Foucault's work in our own, although we had used various

critical and sociopolitical theories. In early drafts of this paper, we used concepts of poststructuralism that were more overarching and broad (e.g., there is no singular Truth). However, as we collaborated through multiple iterations of journal decisions—revisions and rejections, we were increasingly drawn to the ways we saw Panopticism within and among the research on mathematics teacher beliefs (which we elaborate more in a few subsections). Further, we grew deeper understanding of Foucault’s ideas and poststructural thinking, more broadly (for example, Beth co-authored the paper described above (Dubbs & Herbel-Eisenmann, 2021)). We believe (along with the others we have mentioned here) that poststructuralism and Foucault’s work allow us to raise different kinds of questions about the teaching and learning of mathematics, the education of mathematics teachers, and research in mathematics (teacher) education.

Across the articles and book chapter we highlighted here, we can see that several researchers are finding poststructuralist ideas more broadly and Foucault’s ideas specifically useful in raising questions about power and challenging the norms that have been established around the practices of teaching and learning mathematics and the study of those practices. We continue in this section by describing the main tenants of Panopticism and elaborate on how we see it as an appropriate metaphor for mathematics education research. We also describe the participants within the Panopticon of mathematics (teacher) education and some of the ways Panopticism is seen in mathematics education. The conceptions of which mathematics teacher beliefs are “good” and which are deviant is part of the evidence of the Panopticon. Therefore, in this section, we seek to disrupt this normalization and also argue for an expansion of the contexts in which mathematics teacher beliefs are brought into being and reformed, transformed, and/or deformed. We align ourselves with Skott (2009) in arguing that research on teacher beliefs can benefit from a careful consideration of the social contexts in which teachers develop and reform their beliefs. We argue for an interrogation of “context,” however, by examining what is normalized, taken-for-granted, and/or privileged in the uses of particular contexts.

Panopticism

We considered the Panopticon description in Foucault’s (1975/1995) *Discipline and Punish* and expounded on in other works by Foucault (e.g., Foucault, 1980) to interrogate the relationships among researchers, mathematics teachers, contexts, and beliefs. As described briefly in the introduction, the Panopticon was originally developed by Bentham as an architecture to monitor prisoners. Foucault (1975/1995) argued that many systemic institutions can operate in the same way as the Panopticon. He specifically used examples from schooling, mental health institutions, hospitals, businesses, and prisons. Foucault used the Panopticon as a metaphor for these contexts and we, also, follow with extending this metaphor to the context of mathematics teacher beliefs. Foucault (1975/1995) described the Panopticon building in the following way:

At the periphery, an annular building; at the centre, a tower; this tower is pierced with wide windows that open onto the inner side of the ring; the peripheric building is divided into cells, each of which extends the whole width of the building; they have two windows, one on the inside, corresponding to the windows of the tower; the other, on the outside, allows the light to cross the cell from one end to the other. All that is needed, then, is to place a supervisor in a central tower and to shut up in each cell a madman, a patient, a condemned man, a worker or a schoolboy. (p. 200)

Foucault went on to elaborate how it is the perceived gaze of the person in the tower that can function to pressure those in the external cells to conform to particular ways of acting. As they are backlit, their actions are perpetually visible to those in the tower; however, they never know when they are being watched or not (“visible and unverifiable”; Foucault, 1975/1995, p. 201). This

feature of the Panopticon, then, is to “arrange things that the surveillance is permanent in its effects, even if it is discontinuous in its action” (Foucault, 1975/1995, p. 201). That is, even if the people in the tower are not watching, the mechanism itself creates a system in which power is flowing through the system to try to pressure all participants to act in certain ways (including those in the tower).

We argue that mathematics education researchers and teacher educators, as a collective, are centered in the Panopticon being both “visible and unverifiable” (Foucault, 1975/1995, p. 201), while mathematics teachers then are expected to measure, supervise, and correct their behaviors. Panopticism functions such that those engaged in mathematics education govern themselves based on notion of what is “normal.” Schooling, in general, is designed to produce adults who can contribute to society. Although arguments abound about the purposes of schooling (Hochschild & Scovronick, 2003; Labaree, 1997), the expectations frequently include that: at the end of schooling, young adults will be participants in society in ways that conform to a particular set of practices considered to be productive. In fact, society designates those individuals who do not align with these expectations “deviants,” thus, reinforcing the notion there is a norm from which to deviate. With respect to mathematics education and the beliefs of mathematics teachers, a variety of facets are subjected to the regulations and expectations of a particular kind of normality.

The culmination of decades of mathematics education research and teacher education is represented in NCTM’s (2014) *Principles to Actions: Ensuring Mathematical Success for All*. This book has quickly found its place alongside other canonical documents from NCTM such as the *Principles and Standards* (2000) and is used regularly in the contexts of teacher education (professional development and teacher preparation) within the United States. *Principles to Actions* includes a series of tables meant to communicate what beliefs are “productive” and what beliefs are “unproductive.” We provided some examples earlier in the paper; however, there are 39 such pairings of “productive” and “unproductive” beliefs listed in these tables (NCTM, 2014). The message or discourse within the Panopticon is clear that there are only certain beliefs that are considered acceptable.

It is worth noting that the people in the Panopticon are all of those involved in the teaching and learning of mathematics—not just teachers and children. Those participants include: children, youth, and adults learning mathematics; parents of children and youth learning mathematics; mathematics teachers of children, youth, and adults; mathematics teacher educators; mathematics education researchers; mathematics researchers; mathematics specialists; mathematics curriculum writers; professional development providers; school leadership (including principals who frequently are tasked with assessing the quality of mathematics education at their school); school board members (at the local, state and national levels); and (sometimes) legislatures and other governing officials (at the local, state, and national levels).

The reverence accorded NCTM as an organization and *Principles to Actions*, specifically, is evidence of how power is being distributed across the field of mathematics education. The center of the Panopticon then becomes occupied by proponents of NCTM, while the participants in the external cells of the Panopticon police themselves individually and collectively with the slogans, rules, and expectations (or discourses) wielded in the center. Foucault (1980) remarked, “It seems to me power *is* ‘always already there’, that one is never ‘outside’ it, that there are no ‘margins’ for those who break with the system to gambol in” (p. 141). That is, all of those who participate in mathematics teaching and learning, whether centrally or peripherally, are subject to the effects of this power.

It can be easy to surmise that those in control in the Panopticon (i.e. the tower people) are the ones that control the power in the system. Foucault (1975/1995, 1980) clearly argued against this

notion. He stated, “One doesn’t have here a power which is wholly in the hands of one person who can exercise it alone and totally over the others. It’s a machine in which everyone is caught, those who exercise power just as much as those over whom it is exercised” (p. 156). In saying this, he recognized that people have differential positions in the system but the system still operates in ways to try to bind people’s agency. In a later section, we describe how different tools for generating mathematics teacher beliefs show and obscure the way power operates within the Panopticon of mathematics education.

Panopticism and Mathematics Teacher Beliefs Research

We choose to consider the lens of Panopticism as opposed to other principles or ideas for Foucault’s work for several reasons (already alluded to in an earlier subsection). First, we appreciated how the metaphor allowed us to consider the way people engaging in the research about mathematics teacher beliefs (e.g., teachers, researchers) are imprisoned. However, we also seek to raise questions about who is imprisoned by the system (as Foucault raised in his conception of power). It might be easy to conceptualize the Panopticon as imprisoning teachers while researchers (or NCTM) stand guard. The Panopticon operates to try to bind the agency of both prisoners and guards and even the warden is not free from its effects. We see evidence of this structure in mathematics teacher beliefs research when researchers choose particular contexts to survey and when participants use particular discourses to bring their beliefs into being.

Second, we see the use of the metaphor of Panopticon because a prison is run by a set of known and often, written, expectations. In mathematics education discussions about teacher beliefs, we see evidence of written rules like those that have been described from *Principles to Actions* (NCTM, 2014). Examples of unwritten expectations are like the vignettes that open this paper. These rules narrate what counts as a context for teacher beliefs, what beliefs can be brought into being, what beliefs are “good” or productive, and how mathematics teacher educators might feel about particular beliefs.

Third, surveillance is an important key to the operation and function of the Panopticon. We see evidence of surveillance on mathematics teacher beliefs as teachers consent to participate in research. They invite or consent to literal surveillance by cameras and/or people of their classroom environments and the practices therein as well as revealing their thinking, motivations, and other discourses through surveys, interviews, or other research practices. Increasingly, we see calls for greater surveillance of classrooms in the United States (e.g., school board members demanding cameras in every classroom). Surveillance does happen in these overt ways but also in more subtle ones. For example, a teacher might try to tell a researcher what they believe the researcher wants or expects to hear. We see this as connected to surveillance because without the surveillance or presence of the researcher, the teacher would bring different discourses into being around their own considerations of their practices. Although we elaborated briefly on these ideas of imprisonment, rules, and surveillance in separate ways, their functions and operation are all tightly connected in both the Panopticon and the field of mathematics teacher beliefs research.

Contexts and Mathematics Teacher Beliefs

As we considered the data and the existing research on mathematics teacher beliefs, we noticed certain contexts are privileged within mathematics education. We argue for an expansion of what beliefs are considered relevant and what contexts can serve as opportunities to bring beliefs into being and/or transforming, reforming, and/or deforming beliefs. We imagine some contexts are considered part of the “normal” with respect to those contexts which (re)form teacher beliefs. Perhaps most obviously, the act of teaching itself (enacting lessons) is one of those contexts as others (e.g., Aguirre & Speer, 2000; Skott, 2009) have also noted. Similarly, other practices of teaching, including planning and reflecting on lessons, are contexts that interact with teachers’

construction of their selves (e.g., Ambrose et al., 2003; Skott, 2009). Additionally, professional development (e.g., Fennema et al., 1996; Stipek et al., 2001) and teacher education coursework or experiences (e.g., Dede & Karakus, 2014; Swars et al., 2009) are contexts in which teacher beliefs are brought into being and transformed.⁶

Importantly, we argue for extending the conception of these contexts in which normalization about the generation of teacher beliefs occur to include other social contexts, recognizing we are not alone in this desire (e.g., Chan & Wong, 2014; Esmonde & Langer-Osana, 2013; Sztjan, 2003; Valero, 2007). We additionally argue that the beliefs instruments, research settings, and researchers' presence may also shape, resist, and deform teachers' beliefs—thus, the instrument itself is an important context. A teacher's reporting of their practice and beliefs are done with a consideration of who their audience is (Walshaw, 2001). Teachers may be considering what will be valued from the center of the Panopticon when they are communicating about their own actions and beliefs. In this way, the instruments, research settings, and researchers' presence provide an array of possibilities for teachers (who may engage in different ways) to discuss and generate their beliefs about teaching mathematics. Further, the distribution of power across the different instruments for generating beliefs varies.

In this theoretical paper, we adopt Panopticism to consider a range of instruments used to generate data about the beliefs of mathematics teachers. We use examples from the extensive research on 'teacher beliefs' in mathematics education as well as data collected from a small group of teachers across a range of instruments in order to disrupt the taken-for-granted position of power afforded this research historically. Particularly, we explore how 'context' is defined, refined, and expanded across different types of beliefs instruments and how power is distributed within and across these instruments. To accomplish these goals, we will first describe our procedures for collecting and generating data from the existing research and with teachers. Then, we report on what we noticed with respect to contexts and distributions of power. We conclude with a discussion of the contributions the Panoptic lens allowed as well as implications for mathematics education research and teacher education.

Generating Data from the Research

We began looking for research on mathematics education with those papers, chapters, and books we were familiar with from having studied beliefs in mathematics education, collectively and individually, over several years (e.g., Leder & Forgasz, 2002; Pajares, 1992; Philipp, 2007; Silver & Lane, 1995). We were particularly interested in research on mathematics teacher beliefs and, thus, we did not consider research on student beliefs (e.g., Pajares & Graham, 1999; Philipp, 2007). We expanded our searching by investigating the research referenced in the papers, chapters, and books that we began with as well as using search engines with keywords such as "teacher beliefs" and "mathematics education." As we continued reading, we became most interested in how "context" is defined and how power is distributed across and within studies. We, thus, realized that it was important for us to capture a range of the methodologies used to examine, infer, assess, or measure beliefs and did not seek to create an exhaustive list of research (for more exhaustive lists, see Leder & Forgasz, 2002; Speer, 2005). We identified four key types of research representing different places along a continuum from maximum foregrounding of the researcher's discourses (etic) to maximum foregrounding of the teacher's discourses (emic). We stopped expanding our search for research when we found that research was easily identifiable in its position along the

⁶ Just as schooling is a means to control children (Walkerline, 1990), teacher education is a means to control teachers.

etic/emic continuum and that it tended to cluster at the key points. In the Beliefs Instruments: A Panoptic Look section, we describe the etic/emic continuum, the key points along the continuum, and examples of the research.

Generating Data with Teachers

Over a five-year period, the third author collaborated with eight middle grades mathematics teachers. The collaboration focused on mathematics classroom discourse, with an eye toward understanding how action research on mathematics classroom discourse might influence teachers' beliefs and practice over time. For the present article, we, as authors, selected three people on which to focus, Tonya, Jackie, and Lisa (names are pseudonyms). We selected only three because our point is not to make claims about these teacher-researchers but to illustrate our critical noticings about a continuum of beliefs instruments. We picked the three teacher-researchers who teach in the middle grades such that a range of community contexts including a rural school (Tonya), a suburban school (Jackie), and an urban school (Lisa) are represented. The three teacher-researchers also varied in their certification programs as well as the length of time they had been teaching (see Table 1).

TR	Grade	School Setting	Certification	Years Teaching	Curriculum Materials
Tonya	6	Rural, Middle School	Elementary	21	National Science Foundation funded ³
Jackie	8	Suburban, Middle School	Secondary ²	14	National Science Foundation funded
Lisa	8	Urban, Gifted ¹ , High School	Secondary	9	Traditional

Table 1. Description of Teacher-Researchers.

¹ Students in this school scored in the 95th percentile on standardized tests. Students in eighth grade math in this school might be in sixth or seventh grade.

² Jackie also held a master's degree.

³ These National Science Foundation funded curriculum are reform-oriented and student-centered curricular materials.

Belief Instruments Used to Generate Data

Belief Surveys. Each teacher-researcher was administered two different surveys about their beliefs that were available in the field at the time of this project—namely, the QUASAR survey (Silver & Lane, 1995; Silver, Smith, & Nelson, 1995; Silver & Stein, 1996) and the Nature of Math Survey (Adamson et al., n.d.). We used these surveys with permission from the original publishing authors. Teachers completed these surveys in the professional development context, at the request of the research team, at the beginning and end of their professional development sessions. The surveys completed are described in greater detail in a later section.

Belief Arrangements with Accompanying Journal Entries and Interviews. Each teacher-researcher had a set of sticky notes on which they jotted down ideas to capture what was “closest to their heart” in their teaching. Teacher-researchers developed relational mappings of ideas and beliefs (see Figures 1, 2, 3) as well as reflective journals on the mappings. Then, they were interviewed by the third author using a set of common questions (e.g., asking them to talk through their arrangements) and a set of questions that were specific to each teacher-researcher's mapping

(e.g., questions that probed how they were using particular terms like “problem solving” or particular connections they indicated between sticky notes).

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Figure 1. Tonya's belief arrangement. All bolded text and the heart were written by Tonya herself. The sticky notes with bold, italicized text were written by Tonya. The other sticky notes were generated by the researchers. Tonya, however, chose to include them and put them on her arrangement herself.

Figure 2. Jackie's belief arrangement. All connecting lines and the heart shape were drawn by Jackie herself. The sticky notes with bold, italicized text were written by Jackie. The other sticky notes were generated by the researchers. Jackie, however, chose to include them and put them on her arrangement herself.

Figure 3. Lisa's belief arrangement. All connecting lines were drawn by Lisa herself. The sticky notes with bold, italicized text were written by Lisa. The other sticky notes were generated by the researchers. Lisa, however, chose to include them and put them on her arrangement herself. The sad-face emoticon on the sticky note in the upper left was drawn on by Lisa.

Beliefs Instruments: A Panoptic Look

We identified at least four types of prior research on teachers' beliefs and we see these categories as representing different places along an etic/emic continuum. Our discussion of this continuum is not meant to harken back to the 'paradigm wars,' which pit quantitative and qualitative methodological approaches against each other (Gage, 1989) and both against humanities-oriented approaches (Howe, 2009). Instead, we see value in a diversity of paradigmatic stances within the research on mathematics teacher beliefs (Hayes & Doherty, 2017), and we especially see the promise of efforts to bring non-Western ways of knowing into educational research (Martin, 2017; Oppong, 2014). We turn our attention to the distribution of power, a relevant consideration across various ontologies, epistemologies, and axiologies that undergird research that leverages various beliefs instruments.

In other words, we are not necessarily interested in what instruments along this continuum suggest about what is true, how we come to know, or what we value (although the Panopticon metaphor certainly applies to choices of paradigm as well). Instead, we seek to raise questions about *who gets to decide* where contexts relevant to mathematics teaching practice begin and end. Further, we considered how normalized expectations are communicated across the Panopticon of mathematics education and, therefore, how power is distributed within and across the etic/emic continuum. Of note, we did not find research on teacher beliefs in mathematics education that embraced a poststructuralist perspective; therefore, we communicate about the studies described here in structuralist ways offering poststructural connections or language in some places.

Most Etic: Scale Surveys

Existing Research. One way researchers have examined mathematics teacher beliefs is through the use of Likert-scale surveys (Philipp, 2007). This kind of survey has been persistent across the decades of research on teacher beliefs, and often is used by researchers who identify with psychological perspectives. Surveys have allowed for understanding the beliefs of a large group of teachers at a snapshot in time, particularly as they evolved (or not) at different points in time—typically as they progressed through some experience such as professional development (e.g., Fennema et al., 1996; Stipek et al., 2001) or teacher preparation program (e.g., Dede & Karakus, 2014; Swars et al., 2009).

Likert-scale surveys frequently have statements that can be grouped into different categories including beliefs about students, beliefs about mathematics, and beliefs about teaching mathematics. Researchers need to identify relevant categories or contexts in surveys to develop the subscales in a survey, and the categories researchers identify bound the range of what counts as relevant. For example, surveys might have statements about mathematics teaching such as, "Rather than always providing the right answers, teachers should sometimes guide students to the right answers by using appropriate questions" and "The chief role of assessment is to assign grades" (QUASAR instrument; Silver & Lane, 1995; Silver, Smith, & Nelson, 1995; Silver & Stein, 1996). These surveys are given to teachers who then self-report whether they strongly agree, agree, are neutral, disagree, or strongly disagree with the statements.

Similarly, some researchers use semantic differential scales⁷ on their surveys, which ask teachers to place themselves along a spectrum between two opposing (but related) statements or words. For example, on the Nature of Math Survey (created as a part of the ACCEPT project, Adamson et al., n.d.), teachers are given five circles between statement pairs such as "Mathematics

⁷ See <https://conversionxl.com/blog/survey-response-scales/> for more information about these two different kinds of scales.

is an objective, absolute, certain, and consistent body of knowledge” and “Mathematics is a process of inquiry, and a coming to know.” Teachers are asked to select which circle most closely represents their own beliefs. In a few rare cases, the researchers not only identified their subscales (e.g., beliefs about mathematics teaching and learning) but also examined whether these were associated with particular teacher characteristics, including teacher professional background and teacher mathematical knowledge for teaching (Ren & Smith, 2017).

Representing the most etic end of the continuum, the researchers make a maximum number of inferences when using surveys to generate data about beliefs. First, researchers limit possible (re)formation of beliefs for teachers by having prepared items which will only elicit certain discourses within particular contexts. Second, they infer what the teacher meant when responding. For example, on items such as those on the QUASAR instrument, a teacher’s “disagree” or “strongly disagree” can have multiple meanings: 1) the teacher is taking up the discourse of the disagreement of the item (e.g., a strongly disagree with the statement “technology should be used in the classroom” implies a discourse of “technology should not be used in the classroom”) and/or 2) the teacher is rejecting the notion that this discourse applies to her practice (e.g., we should not talk about technology’s role in classrooms). Similar ambiguities arise for other points along the Likert or semantic scales, including the neutral position.

In surveys, perhaps, effects of power flowing from the center of the Panopticon is most evident. Researchers are determining contexts in which teachers are generating beliefs (the instrument itself) and then also determining the range of contexts represented on the instrument. Therefore, the discourse of the instrument itself and the contexts on the instrument are communicating to the teachers about what is relevant in determining their beliefs about teaching, mathematics, and students. Teachers engaging in these instruments might have some preconceived notions of what would be considered normal or valued answers to these survey questions by reflecting on their interactions with researchers or other (mathematics) teacher educators. Teachers have the least opportunity to challenge the flow of power from the center of the Panopticon and still conform to the expectations of filling out the survey as written. They might be extraordinarily deviant and write their own thoughts around the questions (thereby bringing generating new opportunities to (re)form beliefs) but this kind of engagement is unlikely. Further, researchers might disregard their responses in an interest to maintain validity and reliability of an instrument. Both teachers and researchers become bound by the effects of the normalization. In this way, the Likert-scale and semantic differential scale surveys operate as a technology that is similar to the Panopticon.

Teacher-Generated Data. As we considered statements about mathematics, mathematics teaching, and mathematics learning across the Likert or semantic scale belief instruments, we found a range of taken-for-granted contexts implied by the statements. We saw generalized or idealized discourses about mathematics, mathematics teaching, and mathematics learning. In other words, some statements seemed to suggest a Truth about what mathematics, mathematics teaching, or mathematics learning is (i.e., generalized) or should be (i.e., idealized) without consideration of classroom or personal context. These instruments communicated about what is normalized in the process of (re)forming teacher beliefs. For example, consider this item from the QUASAR survey: “Rather than always providing the right answers, teachers should sometimes guide students to the right answers by using appropriate questions” (Silver & Lane, 1995; Silver, Smith, & Nelson, 1995; Silver & Stein, 1996). Because the statement refers to teachers and students broadly, it leaves open possible interpretations that would influence whether a teacher chooses to agree or disagree. Survey-takers may invoke an idealized, generic vision of a teacher and students from any number of contexts and experiences. They may call to mind their own classroom context and an idealized

image of themselves and their students; they might imagine what a teacher they personally know and admire would do; or they might recall an idealized vision of teaching based on something they have read or seen. How survey-takers interpret “sometimes” and their level of agreement with the statement depends on which contexts and vision of teaching they invoke as they are taking the survey. In other words, teachers may agree that this statement reflects something teachers should do generally, even if it does not reflect something that they believe they (should) do in their own classrooms. Such statements rely on an assumption that teachers will extract from unspecified or decontextualized experiences—that is, some generalized discourses about mathematics teaching and learning.

Although idealized and/or generalized contexts were more prominent on the surveys, we saw personal pronouns as indicators that teachers might invoke a more personally contextualized perspective as they completed the surveys. For example, on the Nature of Math survey (Adamson et al., n.d.), the statement, “I see my role mainly as a facilitator,” refers specifically to the survey-taker. Although this statement still required teachers to channel some generalized discourses about mathematics teaching and learning from their experiences, we see this statement as invoking a contextualized discourse about the teacher’s practice rather than a generalized or idealized statement like, “A teacher’s role is mainly as a facilitator.”

In general, researchers cannot know for certain which discourses teachers are (re)forming as they complete beliefs instruments. This uncertainty can be further complicated by inconsistent wording of statements in surveys, particularly as a single survey attempts to capture beliefs about mathematics, mathematics teaching, and mathematics students and their learning. In the Nature of Math survey (Adamson et al., n.d.), teachers were given two related statements designed to reflect dichotomous beliefs and asked to show, along a spectrum, where their beliefs were aligned. Perhaps unsurprisingly, all of the statements in this survey about mathematics were more generalized and lacked references to the people engaged in the mathematical work (see, for example, Herbel-Eisenmann (2007) and Herbel-Eisenmann and Wagner (2007) analyses of pronouns in mathematics textbooks). For example, “mathematics is discovered” (Adamson et al., n.d.) leaves out any references to indicate by whom or in what contexts mathematics is discovered. Different interpretations (e.g., mathematics is discovered by students in my classroom; mathematics is discovered by mathematicians historically and at universities today) might influence survey-takers’ level of agreement with this statement. In this same survey, statements about mathematics teaching and learning were inconsistent. Some statements referred directly to the survey-taker (e.g., “I see my role mainly as a facilitator.”) and others used more generic references to teachers and students (e.g., “It is imperative that students have opportunities to work together with others when solving mathematics problems so that they can learn from one another and learn the mathematics more deeply”). As people and contexts were stripped, inconsistently, from belief statements, the contextualized discourses influencing teachers’ responses become even more opaque.

Focusing on how teachers explain their selections about belief statements might provide some insight into the various contexts they see as relevant to the (re)forming beliefs. For example, in the QUASAR survey, teachers had an opportunity to provide an explanation for their responses, and we looked to those explanations for evidence of the contexts teachers were invoking as they interpreted the statements. Although statements in the QUASAR survey (Silver & Lane, 1995; Silver, Smith, & Nelson, 1995; Silver & Stein, 1996) consistently avoided personal pronouns, the teachers used both personal pronouns (i.e., contextualized discourses) and more generic language (i.e., generalized/idealized discourses) about teachers and students in their explanations. For example, in Figure 4, Jackie’s comment clearly indicated that she was invoking discourses about

herself as a teacher to decide her level of agreement with the belief statement; however, Tonya's comment did not indicate what context(s) she was bringing into being to decide that quality instruction is highly important. Further, Lisa's comment indicates that she brought in a range of experiences to decide her level of agreement with the belief statement. Here, she brought the contexts of mathematics teaching and learning from research and from her own experiences as a teacher to her consideration of the statement.

Item 23: The quality of instruction affects student achievement in mathematics class as much as the student's own ability level.

Teacher	Tonya	Jackie	Lisa
Level of Agreement	Agree	Strongly Agree	Not Sure
Comment	Quality instruction is highly important.	If I don't think I can make a difference, why would I be in the profession?	I've read research to confirm this. I'm not able to be so arrogant in my own classroom.

Figure 4. Responses to Item 23 on the QUASAR survey (Silver & Lane, 1995; Silver, Smith, & Nelson, 1995; Silver & Stein, 1996) following professional development.

Survey items focused primarily on the nature of mathematics as well as what it means to teach and learn mathematics. Therefore, engaging with these instruments only allowed researchers to infer a limited range of social contexts. As the examples we have already given from the QUASAR instrument and the Adamson et al. instrument show, items on these instruments provide teachers an opportunity to engage in contexts that are specifically related to the teaching and learning of students in mathematics. In a later section, we will describe how other contexts are brought into being when more open-ended instruments are used.

We noted, as we considered the possible ranges of interpretations across the survey instruments, there were seldom other examples in the existing mathematics education research that we might use as models. In other words, mathematics education researchers have persisted in data generation and reporting on data in ways that define what is 'normal.' The power of the Panopticon of mathematics education relies on this definition of normal in order to operate to privilege and oppress individuals. People may feel pressured and/or liberated and/or reformed by this distribution of power.

Between Etic and Emic: Open-Ended Surveys

Other kinds of surveys have been developed to understand mathematics teachers' beliefs (Philipp, 2007). A tool developed for the project "Integrating Mathematics and Pedagogy" (IMAP) is an alternative type of survey mathematics education researchers use to infer beliefs (Ambrose et al., 2003). Ambrose et al. (2003) explained their tool by saying, "To avoid the limitations of Likert scales... we developed an instrument in which PSTs [prospective teachers] construct responses instead of choosing from options provided" (p. 35). That is, the IMAP beliefs instrument was designed so teachers did not have to select from already given choices about what they believed but, instead, were able to respond in ways such that researchers believed teachers' beliefs were revealed.

The survey was constructed specifically to elicit teachers' "beliefs about mathematics and mathematics understanding and learning" (Ambrose et al., 2003, p. 35). Focusing the instrument on these specific topics serves a similar purpose as subscales in survey research by narrowing what

might be seen as relevant contexts, but the format provides mathematics teachers more flexibility in terms of how they might respond. For example, teachers were asked to watch a video of a teacher asking a six year old student to solve a story problem. The teachers were then asked a series of open-ended questions such as “Identify the strengths of the teaching in the episode” (Ambrose et al., 2003, p. 36). Each question was presented separately and sequentially. This format allowed researchers to gather evidence about how teachers were making sense of the questions. The researchers then coded the teachers’ responses according to how strongly the teachers seemed to hold beliefs about mathematics and how students developed mathematical understanding (Ambrose et al., 2003). Xenofontos and Kyriakou (2017) have also developed an open-ended survey in order to generate data about mathematics prospective teacher beliefs; however, their emphasis was more focused on beliefs about collaborative problem solving and dialogue.

Open-ended surveys are similar to the Likert and semantic differential scale surveys in the way they evidence the exercise of power from the center of the Panopticon by communicating how teachers should conceptualize their beliefs (based on how questions are posed on the survey) and what should serve as boundaries for those beliefs (what contexts appear on the survey). Teachers have more latitude in their own responses than in the previous category. These responses may be restrained and/or liberated and/or galvanized by the teachers’ consideration of their audience (the researchers) and their interactions with members of that kind of audience. The surveys are technology that functions like the Panopticon.

Between Etic and Emic: Interviews, Observations, and Responses to Teaching Scenarios

Other methods used to examine beliefs include triangulating data from interviews (e.g., reflective, stimulated-recall), observations, and responses to teaching cases (Philipp, 2007). In this kind of research about beliefs, the researcher is often looking for consistency across these various data contexts to infer what teacher(s) believe. Aguirre and Speer (2000), for example, examined videos of classroom teaching as well as interviews to infer the beliefs of secondary mathematics teachers. Specifically, their analyses included observations in which teachers’ beliefs were inferred by the researcher along with detailed analyses of the teachers’ statements in interviews. Many other researchers have studied teachers’ beliefs following a similar pattern of investigation (e.g., Ambrose, 2004; Akkoç et al., 2016; An et al., 2017; Conner et al., 2011; Cross, 2009; Francis, 2015; Speer, 2005). In such data generation strategies, mathematics teachers have flexibility in terms of how they respond to questions in interviews and what practices they employ during observed lessons; however, the researcher ultimately determines what is seen as relevant in terms of beliefs and contexts through questions they ask and their inferences based on responses and observations. Moreover, although some of these researchers gathered many different types of data, in some cases the survey was still given priority in the analysis (e.g., Swars et al., 2009).

Also situated between the etic and the emic is research that combined psychological and social ideas (e.g., how interactions with others related to how beliefs were enacted). These studies were more likely to name contexts beyond those already described in the research as affecting beliefs (namely, the classroom). Skott (2009) argued that, although mathematics education had become increasingly concerned with some of the social factors influencing work in classrooms, this perspective had not permeated the long-standing research on teacher beliefs. Skott identified three communities of practice or contexts that he contended shaped a teacher’s beliefs (the case of Larry at Mellembang).⁸ Gates (2006) and Sztjan (2003) used interviews to link various beliefs to

⁸ The idea that teachers are shaped by particular contexts is evidence of structuralist thinking. For Foucault, social pressures do not (unidirectionally) shape teachers’ beliefs because teachers are not determined by their surroundings.

ideologies that were being enacted. In these cases, the contexts the researchers identified went beyond the boundaries of the classroom and included the school, the community, and beyond.

In these more emic beliefs instruments, individuals are trying to challenge the flow of power from the center of the Panopticon by challenging what is perceived as normal with respect to how beliefs instruments are written and engaged in. The center of the Panopticon though still determines what items are a part of the interviews, observations, and responses to teaching episodes. Further, the individuals are still bounded by expectations of what research on mathematics teaching beliefs looks like or sounds like in the center of the Panopticon. The teachers might be exercising power by the way they participate in these kinds of belief instruments. However, effects of power flowing from the center continue to impact what teachers might count as relevant answers as they attend to who is asking the questions. In other words, the presence of the researcher as well as the presence of the tasks designed by the researcher operate as tools to press the teacher to conform to particular ways of thinking about the generation of their own beliefs about teaching, mathematics, and students.

Most Emic: Teacher-Generated Belief Statements

Beyond the descriptions already reviewed, other researchers have generated data about beliefs by asking teachers to reflect on their own beliefs and write about these beliefs (Herbel-Eisenmann & Cirillo, 2009; Itter & Meyers, 2017). These methods represent the most emic end of the continuum as mathematics teachers themselves are most likely to articulate statements that capture what they see as relevant to what they believe. For example, Herbel-Eisenmann and Cirillo (2009) asked secondary mathematics teachers to jot down statements or draw pictures on sticky notes as they engaged in the work of teaching across a month. In a professional development session, teachers were then asked to arrange the sticky notes on a larger sheet of paper based on how close to the “heart of my [their] teaching” (Boaler & Humphreys, 2005, p. 11)⁹ the ideas on the sticky notes were. A few teachers drew a heart in the center of the larger sheet and arranged some sticky notes inside this heart and others outside of it. Other teachers had different arrangements for their sticky notes. They wrote reflective journals about their arrangements that included descriptions or justifications for their arrangements. Further, the teacher educators working with these teachers also had generated sticky notes with belief statements based on observations and interviews (much like the pattern of inference already described by other researchers) that teachers were asked to consider and, if they agreed, to incorporate these statements into their arrangements (or reject or change, if they did not agree). The teachers added to their reflective journals about the experiences of adding these other statements in and were, subsequently, interviewed about their arrangements. Itter and Meyers (2017) had similarly open-ended prompts, however, they asked their participants to focus only on perceptions and beliefs about mathematics. Despite this limiting focus, we categorize this study on the emic end of the continuum because its open-ended nature still provided teachers with maximum possibilities to bring their own descriptions.

Although at the most emic end of the continuum of instruments for generating teacher beliefs, people in the center of the Panopticon are still exercising power in ways to encourage teachers to self-regulate to particular ways of being. Particularly, teachers will still consider researchers as an audience to their own descriptions of their beliefs. Further, they were asked to communicate these in short ideas and phrases (bringing their own discourses into being). For some of them, these phrases sound like key slogans and generic advice propagated by those in the center of the Panopticon (whether it be the particular researchers in question, the NCTM canon of documents

⁹ It might be worth noting that this is not a NCTM publication but for some teachers and researchers still stands as evidence of what counts as the kind of teaching supported by NCTM.

or other sources of pro-reform teaching). Therefore, while this end of the continuum gives the appearance of the power flowing from the teachers, it can be the most damning evidence of power flowing from the center of Panopticon because of how the power source becomes hidden in what the teachers say and write.

Teacher-Generated Data. In this emic end of the continuum, the belief arrangements and accompanying interviews showed that teachers brought a variety of social contexts into their practices as mathematics teachers. For example, Tonya wrote “students’ families play an important role in students’ success in mathematics” as well as “student, teacher, and family must communicate” as a part of the engagement with the belief arrangements but these contexts were not evidenced on the surveys. Additionally, for Tonya, a teacher’s relationship with administration, for example, suggested that outside factors could decrease a teacher’s confidence and subsequently impact her teaching. On the belief arrangement, Jackie brought discourses such as “learning math should be an enjoyable experience because that will get students intellectually engaged” and “reflective teaching is an attempt to bring your pedagogy/actions into alignment with your stated beliefs or your vision of teaching.” These contexts were outside the scope of what could be captured by the survey instruments further suggesting that the survey instruments may have presented a narrow range of possibilities from which teachers could choose.

Similar to the etic end of the continuum, we found personally contextualized and idealized or generalized contexts in the emic end of the continuum. We might have expected that the personally contextualized discourses were more common; however, this was not true. At times, teachers used personal pronouns in these statements, signaling references to their specific context (contextualized discourse). For example, Jackie referred specifically to herself when she stated, “One of my roles is to help students pull things together” (Figure 2). Other times, teachers wrote more generalized/idealized statements about teaching and learning mathematics. For example, Lisa wrote, “Students should recognize beauty over procedure” (Figure 3). Given the framing of the activity, we saw this idealized statement as rooted in Lisa’s contextualized practice because she generated this statement in the context of her practice with a prompt that described these statements as “the heart of her (contextualized) practice.” However, we recognize that this assumption might be leading us to an incorrect interpretation of how Lisa was bringing contexts into being as she engaged with the beliefs mapping. Perhaps, Lisa was thinking about the students in her gifted and talented class but not the students in her other classes. Her statement also raised questions that lead to different interpretations: How is beauty different than procedure? How is Lisa defining ‘beauty’ here? The messages from within the Panopticon would suggest that Lisa is likely using ‘beauty’ here like NCTM might use ‘conceptual’ and as an opposite to ‘procedural.’ Therefore, was Lisa trying to appease her mathematics education researchers as audience?

When compared with the more emic methods, the belief arrangements and accompanying interviews might have fewer instances of inference on the part of the researcher because the data generation method yields more discourses situated within contexts to examine. For example, Jackie stated that “students build understanding” and that “learning is an active, not a passive, process.” The second sentence can be interpreted as bringing meaning to the first sentences or drawing attention to the word “build” in the first sentence. Together, these sentences might be interpreted as identifying a discourse that is important for Jackie’s teaching is that “students are active builders of their own understandings.” Although interpretations might seem more reliable, the contexts or power which is shaping these teachers’ statements might be more obscured. For example, is the phrase “students build understanding” something that Jackie has inferred from or heard directly from people she considers to be in the center of the (‘reform-oriented’) Panopticon and, therefore, considered it appropriate to parrot or paraphrase here to the research team? What other slogans

might appear on the beliefs arrangements and how do they operate to perpetuate the power from the center of the Panopticon?

Discussion

Adopting a Panoptic perspective across the beliefs instruments, we found that 1) instruments varied with respect to the contexts they brought into being and 2) the Panopticon was always operating to pressure conformity to a defined ‘normal’ which was seen as privileged.

Varied Contexts

The beliefs instruments support a particular conception of what contexts are relevant to generating beliefs about teaching including those that are valued by or perceived as valued by the individuals in the center of the Panopticon. With respect to the range of contexts considered relevant on instruments used to assess, infer, or elicit beliefs, we argue that researchers should be cautious in limiting their conceptions of what affects teaching. For example, we found that teachers brought a more diverse range of contexts to their identifying of their “beliefs” than researchers have ostensibly assumed. A larger range of truths might be revealed in the emic instruments than the truths previously implied by the more closed-ended beliefs instruments (etic). Our analysis of the teachers’ responses to the more emic instruments showed that teachers might draw on their social interactions as parents or teachers in a school system (under demands by administration) as well as many other contexts. Further, we wondered what truths were implied or how power was being exercised by teachers who gave neutral responses to particular survey items.

We found that mathematics education researchers normalized the contexts that seemed bounded by the walls of the classroom. What is gained or lost by assuming a teacher’s beliefs are only impacted by those contexts? Further, we raised questions about how other contexts might influence the beliefs that teachers are generating. Certainly, scholars have attended to questions such as these (e.g., Gates, 2006; Sztjan, 2003). We encourage the pursuit of questions along these lines to perturb the normalization within mathematics education.

Additionally, our analysis suggests that these Likert-scale surveys can benefit from careful attention to the discourse of the prompts including pronoun use. For example, the shift from “I” to “we” or “you” on the instrument’s prompts might be signaling idealized discourses, when the researcher might intend to infer contextualized discourses. A researcher might purposefully elaborate on some prompts in order to make more clear what contexts or discourses a teacher might draw on to respond. Opening phrases, such as, “in my current class, I believe...” or “in my practice, I believe that...” will signal to a teacher that the researcher hopes they will draw on a contextualized discourse when responding. If researchers make more clear the definition of beliefs that they are drawing on, they might also make this definition available to the teachers who are responding to their instruments. In this way, the teachers might better understand what range of contexts are expected (normalized).

Power in the Panopticon

The instruments serve as a context in which teachers are expected to both generate and define their beliefs about teaching, mathematics, and students; however, the instruments offer limited perverse opportunities interrupted by the power flowing from the center of the Panopticon. With respect to the distinction between idealized and contextualized discourses, we argue that, at minimal, researchers cannot be sure if and when idealized/generalized and/or personally contextualized discourses are being brought into being in attempts to gauge beliefs. The framing of statements (e.g., using personal pronouns) or prompts may influence the discourses teachers invoke as they engage with belief instruments, but teachers may draw on experiences that were not

expected by the researcher. Our analysis showed that teachers may draw on personal or classroom experiences even when surveys frame statements in idealized or generalized ways, or they may craft idealized or generalized statements even when prompted to consider their own practice and context. We argue that framing statements as “beliefs” generally privileges idealized or generalized statements about mathematics, mathematics teaching, and mathematics learning. For example, some researchers argue that people are frequently willing to offer their opinion on something, even if they have not thought it through (i.e., have not considered various contexts) (Ambrose et al., 2003). Even when researchers may try to provoke beliefs within particular contexts, we caution researchers that the full range of discourses invoked by teachers during surveys, interviews, and in other belief instruments, is not fully transparent and is constantly under negotiation. Additionally, these range of discourses are being influenced by the expectations for normalization from the center of the Panopticon. Thus, it may be impossible to talk about changes to beliefs, and in particular, to cite the factors impacting what researchers perceive as change. Instead, researchers could consider changes in the discourses brought into being by teachers as they engage with beliefs instruments and recognize the temporality and shifting nature of these discourses.

All points along the etic-emic continuum, as well as a range of possible analytic perspectives, provide opportunities for power to be transformed and (re)made by the participants in the collective of the Panopticon of mathematics education. Consider, for example, Esmonde and Langer-Osuna (2013) and Chan and Wong (2014). The authors in each of these articles have expanded the notions of what beliefs or discourses shape learning in mathematics classroom. In particular, Esmonde and Langer-Osuna (2013) described a figured world of friendship and romance at play in a mathematics classroom and unpacked its resultant implications for mathematical learning opportunities. Chan and Wong (2014) interviewed mathematics teachers about the nature of mathematics and the intersection of mathematics teaching and learning with their own religious practices. Still, these researchers have made decisions about what “counts” as relevant to mathematics education during the design of any instrument to infer, assess, or elicit beliefs, during administration of the instrument, and during analysis of the responses to the instrument. Therefore, in articles written about these tools, researchers can make explicit which assumptions they made during each of the research phases.

These kinds of explanations would allow other researchers to better understand how power is distributed within the instrument itself, the context of taking the instrument, and other aspects of the research process including analysis. Much of the research we reviewed began with a premise that there is a relationship between enacted beliefs and professed beliefs—which is why researchers generated data in multiple contexts (such as interviews and observations). We noted, however, a difference in considering the belief arrangements. The teachers used these arrangements as guides to reflect on their own practices in their classroom contexts becoming a standard to which they held themselves—believing that it was most important for them to bring their practices in the classroom in alignment with the beliefs they professed (Herbel-Eisenmann & Cirillo, 2009). Importantly, it was a tool they had imbued with power but it remains unclear whether power was operating to preserve the normalization of the Panopticon or if it was meant to perturb that normalization. Perhaps, whether they saw it as preserving or perturbing varied from teacher to teacher.

All beliefs instruments operate to preserve the function of the Panopticon and, thus, ostensibly promote an equitable practice for teaching and learning mathematics. We question, however, whether the Panopticon, in practice, functions to promote an equitable practice as it limits the conceptions of mathematics education to those already valued and normalized within the

Panopticon. As Martin (2008) described, mathematics education is influenced by the structural inequities, including White supremacy, in the United States (particularly).

The Panopticon and Teacher Beliefs Research, Revisited

It has been at least 30 years since Foucault's name was first mentioned in the contexts of mathematics education and yet, many aspects of his work remain unexplored in considering the research on and the practice of teaching and learning mathematics. Other critical theories have become more widely used to explore phenomenon from a sociopolitical perspective. In several of the papers using Foucault, we noticed scholars choosing from Foucault's work almost like as a buffet—picking and choosing what to take and what to leave behind. We can see that part of this is because of the nature of Foucault's work, which itself is in somewhat disparate parts across multiple volumes of books (Kolloche, 2016). Part of what we see as a contribution of our paper is using the metaphor of the Panopticon and its ability to support us in capturing a range of principles and ideas inherent in other aspects of Foucault's work. As we discussed previously, the ideas of agency (and deviance), collective expectations for participation, and surveillance are those that we argue are components of the Panopticon and for which we see evidence in the research on mathematics teacher beliefs. Embedded in each of these aspects is the idea of the way power operates within both the Panopticon and the field of research on mathematics teacher beliefs—there are no humans who are free from the influences of how the power is distributed across the system. No one particularly wields this power but all are subject to its influence.

In some sense when we began the work we have presented here, we saw the belief mappings as a way out of the trappings of the system that had produced the kinds of research privileged previously (i.e., Likert surveys, structured interviews or observations). However, as we continued our exploration and used the Panoptic lens we see things are more complex. As noted in the earlier section, although the belief mappings seem like they could be supporting teachers to bring their own beliefs into being, we can see how the power in the system might actually just be obscuring and distorting our view. Are teachers just saying what they think researchers want to hear, parroting the “productive” beliefs that NCTM's (2014) *Principles to Actions* has already characterized for them? It is not that we believe that mathematics teachers are being duplicitous or purposefully evasive but rather that we see none of us is free from the influence of the Panopticon's distribution of power.

Implications for Teacher Education

In addition to implications for research on beliefs, our analysis has implications for our practices in mathematics teacher education. First, teacher educators cannot assume that learning opportunities they offer to teachers are what is changing teachers' beliefs. In short, they cannot assume they control the flow of power. Teacher education with prospective teachers occurs, typically, when they trying out their own beliefs, often for the first time away from their families. Their interactions with new friends and new experiences are likely to have a considerable impact on their practices as they develop understandings of and interact with a more expansive set of people than they may have in their previous education. Teacher education with practicing teachers occurs, typically, as those teachers are constantly negotiating their practice daily with children and youth in their classrooms and as they experience new life events. The evolution of people's lives as it naturally progresses might be as significant as the learning opportunities that mathematics teacher educators devise.

Second, teacher educators could offer teachers learning opportunities that include the exploration of beliefs that have previously been ignored. For example, teachers might explore standards they hold for their own children and standards they hold for the children in their classrooms, the main doctrines of their religion on how to treat people who are different than

them, their beliefs about the purpose(s) of schooling, or their beliefs about leaders. Importantly, any exploration of these discourses or beliefs should be accompanied by an opportunity to consider the range of influences on one's classroom practices. If mathematics teacher educators use restrictive lenses through which to develop beliefs, then they may be missing opportunities to impact the lives of the students in these mathematics teachers' classrooms.

Implications for Other Countries

As we stated early on in this paper, we situate our arguments here from the context that we, as authors, are familiar with—namely, the United States. We believe that some of our observations and recommendations will be relevant for mathematics educators working outside of the United States. We did not specifically limit our examination of beliefs research to that within the United States; however, we did only examine research that is published in English (as it is the only language in which all three of us are fluent). Therefore, our noticings about what kinds of contexts are focused on in beliefs research and the way participating teachers might be drawing on idealized or generalized contexts may be those that also apply to research outside of the United States.

Kollosche, a reviewer of our current manuscript, prompted us to question the assumptions we might have made about how the Panopticon functions across the field of mathematics education research on teacher beliefs internationally. For example, he pointed out that teachers have tenure in Germany and, therefore, might not feel pressured to conform to particular beliefs. Specifically, he stated:

In Austria, Germany, and many other European countries, tenured employment is usual and untenured employment is only legal for a few years. So, most teachers are in a tenured employment. Also, it is very difficult to fire them. Therefore, teachers are not in much pressure to make sure that they keep their jobs or find new ones. Additionally, there is not necessarily an obligation for in-service education, and even if there is, their performance in in-service education and the degree to which changes in their teaching in enacted is hardly monitored and has no consequences on employment. All this leads to a situation in which researchers say that they [sic] insights have too little impact on the classroom, as it is difficult to bring them into the classroom. (D. Kollosche, personal communication, March 4, 2022)

In the United States, there is great variability about the stability of teachers' jobs; however, the majority of teachers do not have the stability guaranteed by tenure. Most teachers are expected to participate in professional development or accrue points for various educative experiences that are required for maintaining licensure. Some teachers have more choices for these than others. We can see how these differences might have implications for how the Panopticon does (not) map to the experiences of mathematics education researchers in other countries. We wonder if mathematics education researchers would face similarities in their interactions with teachers particularly around their beliefs. We argue in this paper that teachers and researchers are pressured by the expectations of the Panopticon and that these pressures lead researchers to constrain the contexts in which teachers generate data about their beliefs and teachers to bring particular beliefs into being. More directly, we wonder if teachers might still use the discourse of particular beliefs because they believe that is what is valued by the researchers. Further, as researchers, we have experienced feedback pressuring us to study particular ideas. For example, in one of Kate's, the first author, early works on the religious ideologies of mathematics teachers, she was advised by a mathematics educator/reviewer that religious identities or beliefs could not be studied via teachers' contributions to group discussions and could only be considered through the teachers' own reflections and descriptions. It is unknown if the reviewer was an international colleague or one

from within the United States;¹⁰ however, it is an example of the way in which researchers are bound by the expectations of the Panopticon. This reviewer had limited conceptions of what could count as work about the beliefs of mathematics teachers and exercised their privilege to reject the paper. We do not think that this kind of dilemma is faced only by researchers within the United States.

Foucault (1975/1995) pointed out that, “Whenever one is dealing with a multiplicity of individuals on whom a task or a particular form of behaviour must be imposed, the panoptic schema may be used” (p. 205). Therefore, it is unsurprising the panoptic schema would be useful in conceptualizing how teacher beliefs come into being and are transformed, measured, and assessed. Together, as a collective, the individuals in the Panopticon perpetuate a normalization of the expectations and rules set forth by those perceived to be in the center of the Panopticon. Indeed, among the external cells of the Panopticon, we find teachers who are policing one another and themselves with respect to the “productive beliefs” purported by the individuals at the center of the Panopticon. We invite ourselves and other educators to consider how we are channeling official discourses from the Panopticon and how power is being made and remade in our fields.

An Afterword: Author Reflections on an Open Review

The publishing of this paper is the end of a long journey with these data, more generally, and with the theoretical conceptualizations we present here, particularly. These data were originally generated during the 2005-06 school year as part of Beth’s National Science Foundation CAREER grant. Since then, Beth, and then Kate, and then Frances have been intrigued by the possibilities of looking across the data generated about the participants’ beliefs. We have used these activities (both the surveys and the belief arrangements) in a multitude of teacher education settings with prospective and practicing mathematics teachers. Some initial analyses of the belief arrangements were the central component to Kate’s practicum study (the smaller early-in-the-program study one might do as a part of doctoral work) beginning in 2010.

After separate discussions, we collectively returned to this work in earnest in late 2015. We began anew—wondering what frames and lenses we could bring to explore what we had collectively and individually pondered after multiple iterations of the uses of these tools. Those discussions in late 2015 and early 2016 led us to a consideration of poststructuralism from a Foucauldian perspective. As noted in the paper, we were all novices in our drawing on Foucault but appreciated the ways his poststructuralist principles allowed us to see new things about what we had been pondering for years. We had read and used other research and theories grounded in poststructuralist ideas which facilitated our work as we supported one another, analyzed the data, and co-authored a first version of a manuscript. In fall of 2017, we submitted it for the first time and celebrated. At this first journal, we received two revise and resubmit decisions from the handling editor before they then rejected it. Although we felt the revisions were items we could incorporate, the editor clearly stated that the primary reason for the rejection was because it is not good policy to allow for a third round of revisions. We still wonder, however, about the efforts we exerted in the first two rounds of revisions and whether we were close or still so very far when the editor rendered this decision. After this work with the first journal, we were immediately desk rejected by the next journal with some minimal feedback about how the work read as two papers. Then, as the COVID-19 pandemic began in 2020, we revised the paper to be a theoretical investigation, submitted it, and waited a year for a reject decision. Along all of these submissions,

¹⁰ Given where this work was under review, it is highly likely it was reviewed by a scholar outside of the United States. We will not provide other details in an effort to preserve anonymity.

we considered the feedback that was helpful from the reviews, read more, worked and re-worked, revised and re-conceptualized the manuscript. At a few points in this journey of revisions, we also sought out expertise from people well-renowned for their work using Foucault in educational research. They supported us by reading the paper and giving detailed feedback about the ways our writing might have undermined our use of Foucauldian principles but also, importantly, describing how our work reflected engagement with Foucault that would be considered consistent with his principles. Through these revisions and alongside other work we were undertaking, we increased our expertise of the fledgling ideas we had used and points we tentatively asserted in early versions of the manuscript about poststructuralism. We began to realize that Panopticism was really capturing what we felt we were grappling with.

In the summer of 2021, when we, again, were revisiting this paper and the most recent round of feedback, the call for manuscripts for the new *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education (JTM-ME)* had circulated in our inboxes. We worked to address some of the feedback from the latest rejection decision and sent in our manuscript, perhaps mostly exhausted and not very hopeful, even though we thought the manuscript contributed important reflections on the study of teacher beliefs in mathematics education. The editor at *JTM-ME* responded enthusiastically to the piece and, honestly, my (Kate's) heart had a much-needed boost. We share this story as backdrop to our ensuing reflections on the open review because it was these experiences that led us to choose an open review. We had already received rounds of feedback from nameless and faceless reviewers who, at times, misunderstood our efforts and perhaps weary from many things, were not sure how to support us (the nameless and faceless authors) in our quests to use poststructuralism and articulate our thinking and arguments around the mathematics teachers' beliefs research.

David Kolloche was assigned to review our paper with the notation that he "has written on Foucault in the past and is knowledgeable about the literature relevant to your manuscript" (A. Moore, October 7, 2021, personal communication). We were both excited and hesitant to hear his thoughts on our work as we had faced the mixed messages and rejections from earlier reviewers, some of whom had self-identified or been referenced to as experts in Foucault.

Kollosche wrote at length, clearly having deeply engaged with our manuscript, the arguments we were making, and how to support us in moving the manuscript forward toward publication. We have already mentioned in the discussion of the article some of the ways that Kolloche pushed our thinking, particularly related to our U.S. centric assumptions. Kolloche offered perspectives that were more overarching in nature as well as feedback that was more locally grounded in different sections of the manuscript. He pointed us to articles that we might otherwise have not found which helped inform our new revisions. We appreciated that he pointed out places in which we might bump up against other scholars' work and helped us see that we needed to be clearer.

It is perhaps important to point out that one of the main points that Kolloche raised was around our use of Panopticism. In his initial review, he encouraged us to consider different ideas from Foucault's work. We experienced some tension as we considered his feedback as the person "knowledgeable about the literature" (A. Moore, October 7, 2021, personal communication) and our own developed senses and commitments because Panopticism helped us interpret what we saw in the data in ways that captured what we wanted to communicate to readers. As we worked to consider his feedback, we appreciated the way it allowed us an opportunity to more clearly articulate why we chose Panopticism, particularly, from the many ideas Foucault might have offered. We believe our revised article described our perspectives, even if they remain in tension with Kolloche's advice to choose something different.

We appreciated the open review process as it allowed us to understand who was providing us feedback and how our relative positionalities could come into that interaction. We saw Kolloosche as certainly knowledgeable about Foucault, but it was this same understanding that supported us, as authors, in digging into our own perspective and arguing for Panopticism in a different way than we might have if Kolloosche remained a nameless and faceless reviewer. We found courage in knowing him and the scholarly contributions he has made, and we were still pushed to clarify our argument in the manuscript. After seven years of working on this manuscript and over 17 years considering the tools and theoretical conceptions of mathematics teacher beliefs, we are grateful this manuscript has found its home.

One final set of wonderings as we step back and reflect on the last seven years of battling to find this paper its home. This experience has led us to question some of the assumptions that are made throughout the publication process. Although we know that the review process (both opened and masked) has pushed us to improve our work, it also depends on an assumption that reviewers are right, more knowledgeable, and/or have the “correct” interpretations of ideas or methods. We, as authors, can find ourselves chasing our tails trying to please the reviewers, who are usually nameless and faceless, and who sometimes provided minimal critique for their recommendation to reject our paper. We have been affirmed in side conversations with people who are particularly Foucault experts (in this case, outside of math education) while simultaneously being told that we chose incorrectly from Foucault’s principles or that we were interpreting Foucault incorrectly by reviewers. We have wondered if we were too tentative in some of our assertions in the early stages of this work as we collectively approached it with a lot of humility knowing we had not published about Foucault yet. We wondered then too how people are supposed to begin a work such as this—theoretically engaging deeply with a poststructuralist philosopher. We discussed questions such as, Who is policing the boundaries of poststructuralist analyses? Who is admitted as experts and who is left behind? After persisting for seven years to release this paper and its contributions into the world, each of us has our own feelings about whether or not it has been worth it. We remain uncertain as to whether or not we will continue to pursue engagement with poststructuralist philosophies in our future work, but we find a sense of hope that *JTM-ME* will provide an accessible space for us and other scholars to engage in scholarly dialogue that promotes provocative and innovative (and dare we say, humble) engagement with theory and philosophy.

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